

Reactor Power Monitoring using Cherenkov Radiation with a Commercial Camera System

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ABSTRACT

Reactor safety systems are designed with redundancy, diversity, and independence to ensure reliable monitoring of critical parameters, such as power and fuel or coolant temperature. Among these, reactor power serves as a fundamental indicator of reactor behavior, directly reflecting changes in core reactivity and thermal conditions. In this study, we focus on reactor power as a key parameter and investigate alternative approaches for its measurement that can complement or enhance conventional instrumentation. Reactor power is typically measured using neutron and gamma detectors, such as ionization and fission chambers. While effective, these instruments are expensive, prone to radiation damage, and often exhibit substantial signal noise, particularly at high power levels. To address these limitations, this work demonstrates a cost-effective and non-intrusive optical technique for reactor power monitoring based on Cherenkov radiation emitted in the reactor pool. A GoPro HERO13 camera was used to record video of the core in the University of Texas TRIGA Mk-II research reactor. The blue-channel intensity extracted from the video was calibrated against the power data displayed on the facility's console, establishing a quantitative relationship between optical intensity and reactor power. The results reveal a strong and consistent correlation, with the optical signal showing significantly lower noise than the existing neutron detectors at high power. This study validates the feasibility of using commercial-grade cameras as an independent, low-cost, and low-noise supplementary system for reactor diagnostics and digital twin applications.

Keywords: Cherenkov radiation, TRIGA reactor, Detection, Power monitoring, Reactor safety, Transient

1. INTRODUCTION

Accurate and reliable power monitoring is fundamental to safe nuclear reactor operation, and international safety standards emphasize the principles of redundancy, diversity, and independence in these monitoring systems [1, 2]. While traditional neutron and gamma detectors are well-established, they can suffer from high signal noise, limited operational lifetime, and significant cost. For fission chambers in particular, depletion of the internal fissile material will limit detector longevity [3]. This study explores a complementary method for reactor power monitoring based on measuring Cherenkov radiation with a low-cost, commercial-grade camera system.

The experimental work for this project was conducted at the TRIGA Mk-II research reactor at the Nuclear Engineering Teaching Laboratory (NETL). This facility has been operated by The University of Texas at Austin since 1992. Like most TRIGAs, it uses uranium-zirconium hydride (U-ZrH) fuel, which provides a strong, prompt negative temperature coefficient of reactivity, making the reactor inherently safe [4]. Power is monitored by three independent nuclear instrumentation systems (NM-1000, NP-1000, and NPP-1000) from startup to full power. The NM-1000 utilizes a fission chamber while the other two incorporate ionization chambers [5]. Although the reactor is licensed to operate at a steady-state power of 1.1 MW [5], signal noise from these detectors at high power levels often constrains practical

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operation to approximately 900 kW to avoid spurious safety scrams. This operational limitation highlights the need for complementary monitoring techniques that are more stable at high power.

Cherenkov radiation intensity is directly proportional to a reactor's fission power, making it a viable indicator of core activity [6]. Previous research has validated this principle using specialized equipment like photodiode arrays [7], silicon photomultipliers (SiPMs) [8], and optical fibers [9]. However, these approaches often rely on expensive or intrusive hardware, such as in-core optical fiber installation. This work proposes a non-intrusive, cost-effective alternative by using a GoPro HERO13 camera. The system provides an independent monitoring channel with reduced noise at high power and much higher temporal resolution than the existing console instrumentation, directly addressing IAEA recommendations for enhancing reactor safety.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

Cherenkov radiation is an electromagnetic phenomenon, first characterized by Pavel Cherenkov, that is observed in open-pool reactors as a characteristic blue glow [10]. It is emitted when a charged particle travels through a dielectric medium, such as water, at a speed greater than the phase velocity of light in that medium. For pure water (refractive index ≈ 1.33), this condition is met for electrons with kinetic energies above 250 keV [11].

The spectrum of Cherenkov radiation is biased towards lower wavelengths because the number of photons generated per unit path length is proportional to the frequency. This results in a higher intensity in the blue and ultraviolet regions of the spectrum, which explains the familiar glow. Furthermore, visible photons have a mean free path exceeding 10 meters in water, allowing the light to be transmitted with minimal attenuation, which makes it ideal for remote monitoring from the pool surface.

The light's intensity is primarily driven by prompt gamma rays emerging from fission events [12]. These gammas travel from the fuel into the surrounding water, where they generate energetic Compton electrons. These secondary electrons are the main source of the Cherenkov glow. While other radiation, such as beta particles from fission product decay, also possesses sufficient energy, their contribution is minimal. This is because most beta particles are absorbed within the fuel elements or cladding before they can reach the water.

The foundational principle for this work is the confirmed proportionality between the total Cherenkov light intensity and the reactor's power [6]. This direct, linear relationship, which is most accurate when power is high compared to decay heat, establishes the physical basis for using the optical glow as a reliable, non-invasive proxy for reactor power.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Experimental Setup and Data Acquisition

A GoPro HERO13 camera was placed inside an underwater housing and mounted to the bridge above the pool of the TRIGA. The lens was positioned just below the pool surface with a direct line of sight to the core approximately 7 m below [13]. This setup is shown in Figure 1. Two datasets were collected: video from the GoPro and operational data from the reactor console. The videos were captured at a resolution of 1,920 x 1,080 pixels at a frame rate of 30 frames per second (fps). The console data (power, temperatures, rod positions), shown for a typical operational day in Figure 2, were logged via a serial connection using the ZOC Terminal, which is an SSH client developed to communicate with the reactor control systems [14].

3.2. Baseline Detector Noise Characterization

The power levels throughout the operational range were recorded and analyzed to quantify the noise in the signals from the reactor console. Specifically, the reactor was held at various steady-state power levels, from 1 W to 900 kW, for at least six minutes each. This was done in both *Auto* mode (where a PID controller adjusts the regulating rod) and *Manual* mode. The standard deviation of the power signal was calculated for each interval to serve as a metric for noise.

Figure 1. GoPro camera system mounted at the reactor pool bay overlooking the core.

Figure 2. Example of TRIGA console data for a full day of operation, showing power, control rod positions, and temperatures. This data from 5/1/25 can be accessed at https://nuclear-twins.tacc.utexas.edu/data_by_date.

As shown in Figure 3, the absolute noise (standard deviation) increases with reactor power in both control modes. The relationship is sublinear which indicates that the noise grows slower than the power itself. This sublinear scaling means the relative noise decreases at higher powers, but the absolute fluctuations still become significant enough to impact operations near the licensed limit. The Auto

mode could have less noise than the manual mode since the PID controller can smooth out fluctuations [15]. This analysis provides a quantitative baseline to compare with the power estimates derived from the Cherenkov radiation.

Figure 3. Standard deviation (noise) of the detector power signal as a function of reactor power under (a) Auto and (b) Manual control modes.

3.3. Video Data Analysis Workflow

The video data was processed through a multi-step workflow designed to extract a clean, calibrated power signal.

3.3.1. Preprocessing and Time Synchronization

First, the raw video was spatially cropped to the region of interest around the core, and the blue channel was extracted and converted to a grayscale intensity time series, x_t . The reference power signal from the reactor, y_t , was resampled to a matching temporal grid. To align the two signals, the optimal time lag τ^* was found by maximizing the normalized cross-correlation (NCC), which was computed using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT):

$$\tau^* = \arg \max_{\tau} \left(\frac{1}{M} \sum_{t=1}^M \frac{(y_{t+\tau} - \mu_y) \cdot (x_t - \mu_x)}{\sigma_y \sigma_x} \right) \quad (1)$$

where μ and σ are the mean and standard deviation of the respective signals over the correlation window of length M .

3.3.2. Per-Pixel Calibration and Selection

A simple full-frame average of pixel intensities proved insufficient, as it included noise from reflections and non-core regions. To improve fidelity, a per-pixel calibration was performed. Two anchor windows were defined in the training data: one at low power and one at high power. For each pixel i , a linear mapping was determined to align its average intensity values, $\bar{x}_{i,1}$ and $\bar{x}_{i,2}$, with the corresponding average reactor powers, \bar{y}_1 and \bar{y}_2 . This yields pixel-specific scaling coefficients, a_i and b_i :

$$a_i = \frac{\bar{y}_2 - \bar{y}_1}{\bar{x}_{i,2} - \bar{x}_{i,1}}, \quad b_i = \bar{y}_1 - a_i \bar{x}_{i,1} \quad (2)$$

The Mean Squared Error (MSE) between the calibrated pixel signal and the reference power was then calculated for every pixel. The spatial distribution of this error is shown in the heatmap in Figure 4. The map clearly shows that pixels directly over the reactor core (darker regions) have a much lower error and a stronger correlation with power. Selecting too few pixels increases noise, whereas including too many makes the reconstructed signal approach the screen average. Hence, only the top 10% of pixels exhibiting the strongest correlation with reactor power were utilized for the final signal reconstruction.

Figure 4. Heatmap of the relative Mean Squared Error (MSE) for each pixel after linear calibration. Darker regions indicate lower error and better correlation with reactor power, highlighting the most informative pixels over the core.

3.3.3. Final Signal Reconstruction

The final video-derived signal was constructed by averaging the intensities of the pixels selected in Section 3.3.2. A final quadratic correction was applied to this averaged signal to account for non-linear effects, such as camera sensor saturation at high intensities, ensuring accurate tracking across the full dynamic range.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The analysis was performed on a dataset divided into training and testing segments.

4.1. Full-Frame Averaging Baseline

As an initial test, the reactor power was estimated by averaging the intensity of all pixels in each frame. As shown in Figure 5, this simple approach captures the overall power transient, but significant deviations are present, particularly during the power ramp-up. The residual error is large, highlighting that many pixels do not correlate well with reactor power. This motivates the necessity of the selective pixel analysis described previously.

4.2. Optimized Pixel Selection and Calibration

Using the selected pixels, the scaling coefficients and the quadratic adjustment parameters were derived from a training dataset. This dataset was a monotonic power ramp, spanning the operational range of the reactor. Figure 6 shows the excellent agreement between the detector power and the final calibrated video signal. During a high-power steady interval (500–650 s), the detector signal had a standard deviation of 11.6 kW, while the calibrated video signal's standard deviation was only 7.1 kW, a significant

Figure 5. Comparison between detector power and a video signal derived from averaging all pixels. The large residual error highlights the need for pixel selection.

reduction in noise.

The calibration model was then applied to the unseen testing dataset, which contained more complex power transients. As shown in Figure 7, the Cherenkov-derived power continues to track the detector measurement with high fidelity, demonstrating that the model generalizes well.

A quantitative noise comparison on the testing data is provided in Table I. At low power levels (e.g., 10 kW to 50 kW), the video signal has higher noise than the detector. However, at high power (950 kW), the video signal's standard deviation is nearly half that of the detector (5.95 kW vs. 10.06 kW). This confirms the optical method's better stability in the high-power region where signal reliability is most critical.

Table I. Noise (Standard Deviation) Comparison for Selected Intervals from the Testing Dataset.

Time Interval	Target Power (kW)	Detector Noise (kW)	Video Noise (kW)
14:50 – 14:52	700	9.75	10.32
14:54 – 14:57	50	0.97	2.35
14:59 – 15:04	550	7.32	4.94
15:05 – 15:07	950	10.06	5.95
15:09 – 15:11	300	4.37	4.22
15:12 – 15:15	600	9.65	9.37
15:17 – 15:21	10	0.43	2.00

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates that a commercial camera can serve as a robust, low-cost, and non-intrusive instrument for monitoring reactor power via Cherenkov radiation. The optical method provides a signal

Figure 6. Comparison of detector power and the calibrated video-derived power for the training dataset. The final calibrated signal (green) closely tracks the detector signal (blue) after selecting the best pixels and applying a quadratic correction.

Figure 7. Validation on the testing dataset, showing close agreement between the detector power (blue) and the calibrated Cherenkov-derived power (orange) during transients.

that has reduced noise than conventional detector channels at high power. We will continue to explore the potential of this approach in various reactor environments and test at higher power levels for further validation. This approach directly supports IAEA recommendations for diversity and redundancy in reactor safety instrumentation.

Further work will focus on overcoming the primary limitation of battery life by integrating underwater cameras capable of continuous data transmission. Furthermore, extending the methodology to a network of multiple cameras could enable non-invasive 2D/3D core flux mapping, offering new possibilities for real-time reactor diagnostics and visualization. A future application involves using the camera as an independent, diverse signal to filter the primary instrumentation data. By cross-correlating the two signals, true physics-based power fluctuations (which would appear in both) can be decoupled from stochastic electronic noise (which would be uncorrelated). This “true” noise signal could then be used to train a digital twin or advanced controller, ensuring it actuates based on physical reality rather than instrument artifacts.

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